

Influence of timber moisture content on wave time-of-flight and longitudinal natural frequency in coniferous species for different instruments

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Abstract: Non-destructive techniques (NDTs) are well suited for rapid estimation of timber properties, but NDT results are affected by several factors, the most important of which is the moisture content (MC) of wood. Much research in this context was limited to ultrasound measurement of a few wood species, mainly to Norway spruce. The present paper investigates the MC influence on the NDT results obtained by instruments based on ultrasound (2 devices), impact stress waves (1 device), and longitudinal vibrations (2 devices). 100 large cross-section specimens of four timber species were tested, namely: radiata pine, Scots pine, Salzmannian pine and maritime pine. The influence of MC on velocity was found to be stronger below the fiber saturation point (FSP) than above FSP. MC adjustment factors below FSP are proposed for these wood species.

Keywords: Longitudinal vibration, moisture content, non-destructive testing, stress waves, time-of-flight, ultrasound waves.

Introduction

The results of non-destructive testing (NDT) are affected by several factors: moisture content (MC), temperature, the length of the specimens, sensor positioning, timber-sensor coupling, grain angle, just to mention a few. The NDT factors and mechanical properties were intensively investigated (Kollmann and Krech 1960; James 1961; Bucur 1980; Gerhards 1982; Sandoz 1991; Moreno-Chan 2007; Biechele et al. 2011; Arriaga et al. 2012, 2014, 2017; Casado et al. 2012; Yoshihara 2012a,b; Ozyhar et al. 2013; Xu and Wang 2014; Denzler and Weidenhiller 2016; Llana et al. 2016;). According to Sanabria et al. (2011), the MC effect in case of air-coupled ultrasonic devices is still not clear, though the influence of MC is well recognized at the very beginning of wood research. Chevandier and Wertheim (1848) tested 14 wood species and obtained correction factors from 0.5% (ash) to 1.3% (Scots pine) per 1% MC change on longitudinal velocity obtained by resonance acoustic methods. Several authors found a much stronger MC influence on ultrasound wave velocity ($UWVel$) below the fiber saturation point (FSP) (Sakai et al. 1990; Kang and Booker 2002; Oliveira et al. 2005; Bucur 2006; Gonçalves and Leme 2008). Sandoz (1993) estimated that the MC influence is 8 times stronger below the FSP. A similar effect was seen on stress wave velocity ($StWVel$) (Wang 2013). Matthews et al. (1994) observed different MC effects on $StWVel$ of softwoods and hardwoods. Íñiguez-González et al. (2015) determined MC correction factors as velocity decrement per 1% MC increase (Vel_{decr}/MC_{incr}) in engineering wood constructions. Sandoz (1989) observed 0.80% Vel_{decr}/MC_{incr} in the range of 5 - 30% MC, while Switzerland-sourced Norway spruce beams of different sizes were tested with the instrument Steinkamp BP-V (Ultratest, Germany). Other authors applied the Steinkamp BP-V for Scots pine grown in Spain and found a 0.70% Vel_{decr}/MC_{incr} in the MC range of 12 - 28% MC (Rodríguez-Liñán and Rubio 2000). Gonçalves and Leme (2008) used the Steinkamp

BP7 device (Ultratest, Germany) with 45 kHz transducers on 30 x 60 x 300 mm³ pieces of Parana pine grown in Brazil and detected 0.45% Vel_{decr}/MC_{incr} . Steiger and Arnold (2009) described results for Norway spruce (Sylvatest device, CBS-CBT, Switzerland) with 0.53% Vel_{decr}/MC_{incr} below 28% MC. A 0.61% Vel_{decr}/MC_{incr} was proposed for 41 x 98 x 4500 mm³ Norway spruce boards by Unterwieser and Schickhofer (2011) for the UWVel device Sylvatest (CBS-CBT, Switzerland) and longitudinal vibration (LVibr) device ViSCAN (Microtec, Italy). Montero et al. (2015) proposed linear Vel_{decr}/MC_{incr} factors for Scots pine for different instruments: 0.48% Sylvatest Trio (CBS-CBT, Switzerland, UWVel based), 0.50% MicroSecond Timer (Fakopp Enterprise, Hungary, impact stress waves (ImpStW) based), and 0.65% Portable Lumber Grader (Fakopp Enterprise, Hungary, longitudinal vibrations (LVibr) based), while the wood pieces had the dimensions of 100 x 150 x 3000 mm³. Gonçalves et al. (2017) tested two hardwoods (50 x 100 x 3500 mm³; USLab, Agricef, Brazil, device) and proposed 0.66% linear Vel_{decr}/MC_{incr} factor for saligna gum and 0.83% for lemon-scented gum in the 9 - 30% MC range.

Other authors proposed dynamic modulus of elasticity (MOE_{dyn}) correction factors calculated as the product of density and Vel^2 . According to Nocetti et al. (2015), MOE_{dyn} decreased by 0.58% in 80 x 80 x 2500 mm³ pieces of sweet chestnut, and Unterwieser and Schickhofer (2011) reported 0.83% MOE_{dyn} decrement per % MC_{incr} for Norway spruce.

The goal of the present study was to determine linear velocity decrement factors for the most widely used structural timber species in Spain, which will be observed by instruments based on ultrasound (2 devices), impact stress waves (1 device), and longitudinal vibrations (2 devices).

Material and methods

Materials: 100 planed large cross-section specimens were tested for four species (25 of each): radiata pine (*Pinus radiata* D. Don), Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.), Salzmannian pine (*Pinus nigra* Arnold ssp. *salzmannii* (Dunal) Franco), and maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster* Ait. ssp. *mesogeensis* Fieschi & Gaussen) of Spanish provenance with nominal dimensions of 3000 mm long pieces with 100 x 150 mm² cross-section. Wet specimens were selected in the sawmill and their ends were sealed to promote uniform drying (Figure 1).

NDT experiments: The air drying needed 116 to 180 days. NDT were repeated 7 to 12 times (at each stages) during the air drying process. The longitudinal stress waves (LStW) method was performed via the time-of-flight (TOF) system and longitudinal vibration (LVibr) tools. Three different TOF devices (Figure 2, left) and two LVibr tools (Figure 2, right) were used. TOF data were collected via three commercial devices: two ultrasound waves (USW) devices, 1. i.e. the Sylvatest Duo (SyLDuo) (CBS-CBT, Switzerland) instrument equipped with conical 22 kHz sensors, 2. the USLab (Agricef, Brazil) instrument equipped with conical 45 kHz sensors, and 3. an impact stress waves (ImpStW) device [MicroSecond Timer (MST), Fakopp Enterprise, Hungary]. Natural frequency data were recorded by means of two commercial devices: 1. the Portable Lumber Grader (PLG) (Fakopp Enterprise, Hungary) equipped with a non-contact sensor (a microphone placed in front of one end) and 2. the MTG 960 (Brookhuis, The Netherlands) equipped with an accelerometer contact sensor. Velocity from TOF was calculated by dividing length over TOF. Velocity from the first mode natural frequency was calculated as the product of two times length and frequency.

Moisture content (MC) determination: The oven dry method according to standard EN 13183-1 (2002) was applied, while the specimen slice was free of knots and resin pockets according to EN 408 (2012). Furthermore the mass of whole specimens was recorded during each NDT. With both values (specimen whole mass and the dry slice mass), the MC at each ND measurement stage was estimated. For these determinations a Dry Big 2002971 (JP Selecta, Spain) oven and the two scales from the MTG 960 device were available.

Results and discussion

Table 1 summarizes measurements (stages), the number of days before the first measurement, MC of the stage, velocity calculated from TOF via the Sylvatest Duo, USLab and MST devices, and velocity calculated from frequency obtained by the PLG and MTG devices. MC mean values varied from values above FSP to values close to 9%, depending on species. At the beginning of tests, the MC values were very dispersed and variable. The mean values of velocity obtained from TOF and frequency varied according to species, and coefficients of variation (COV) were similar from the first to the last stages.

The influence of MC on velocity (*Vel*)

Figure 3 shows the *Vel* tendency with MC changes for each device in the four different species. In Figure 3 two different tendencies are illustrated for $MC < FSP$ and $MC > FSP$. This is in agreement with literature data presented in the Introduction. Results of TOF measurements were different depending on the three devices tested. The difference between the two ultrasound waves devices could have several reasons or reasons combination. The first reason is, the transducer-frequency differences (USLab 45 kHz; Sylvatest Duo 22 kHz). The second reason lies in the differences concerning the stop timer thresholds (Brashaw et al. 2005). The third reason is the signal power, which could also explain the different findings in comparison with the impact stress waves device.

The results from the longitudinal vibration devices are almost identical, and the differences between the results are statistically insignificant. These observations are expectable, as the method consists of inducing vibration with a hammer and recording the natural frequency. As measurements with both devices were done simultaneously, the frequency should be the same, but only the way how each device records frequency was different (PLG: microphone; MTG: contact accelerometer). Moreover, most of the measurements were done below FSP (except for Salzmannian pine).

Statistically significant differences were found between velocities in species below the FSP. However, differences in velocity tendency slopes of the different species were not statistically significant. Therefore, only one model was developed, which presents the same slope (coefficient *a*) for the four species, but different constant term values (coefficients *b*, *c*, *d* and *E*) depending on the species. This is a way of expressing four single regression models (one for each species) by means of one equation. The model below 30% MC is expressed by Eq. 1 and the corresponding statistical data are presented in Table 2.

$$Vel = a \cdot MC + b \cdot Z_{rad} + c \cdot Z_{sco} + d \cdot Z_{lar} + E \quad (\text{Eq. 1}),$$

where: *Vel*; velocity obtained from TOF or longitudinal frequency (m s^{-1}); *Z_{rad}*, *Z_{sco}*, and *Z_{lar}* are for radiata pine, Scots pine, and larch pine, respectively, which are only for the tree in question equal 1, and for all other trees are 0. Concerning maritime pine, all *Z* values are 0. As the *P*-value in the ANOVA table is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant relationship between velocities and MC at a 95% confidence level. According to Table 2, velocities decreased from 30 to 36 m s^{-1} . These values are similar to the 32 m s^{-1} given by other authors for radiata pine (55 mm x 80 mm and 1.2 m long) obtained by the WoodSpec resonance-based device (Industrial Research Limited IRL, New Zealand) in the MC range from 17% to FSP (Moreno-Chan et al. 2010).

Correction factors for MC

The goal was to gain general applicable NDT data for the four pine species. The correction factors for some NDT results to a standard 12% MC are presented below, which were calculated by means of Eq. 1. The proposed model is the Eq. 2 and the data are listed in Table 3:

$$Vel_{12} = Vel_{MC} / [1 - k_{MC} \cdot (MC - 12)] \quad (\text{Eq. 2}),$$

where: Vel_{12} ($m s^{-1}$) obtained from TOF or longitudinal frequency at 12% MC, Vel_{MC} ($m s^{-1}$) obtained from TOF or longitudinal frequency at a given MC%, k_{MC} correction factor.

The results in Table 3 can be classified in two groups of species with similar coefficients (radiata and Scots pines vs. Salzmanian and maritime pines). Obviously, the data are species specific. The density of the Salzmanian-maritime pine group is ca. 15% higher than that of the radiata-Scots pine group, and their correction coefficients are also higher. For the Sylvatest Duo device, correction factors from 0.61 to 0.75% Vel_{decr}/MC_{incr} were found in the 10 to 30% MC range. These values are slightly higher than those proposed by other authors obtained with the same device: 0.53% in Norway spruce (Steiger and Arnold 2009), 0.60% in Norway spruce (Unterwieser and Schickhofer 2011), and 0.48% in Scots pine (Montero et al. 2015). When these values are compared with those obtained by other ultrasound waves devices, they are lower than in case of the Steinkamp BP-V device: 0.80% in Norway spruce (Sandoz 1989) and 0.70% in Scots pine (Rodríguez-Liñán and Rubio 2000), and higher than the 0.45% factor proposed for the Steinkamp BP7 device for Parana pine (Gonçalves and Leme 2008). Concerning the MST device, the correction factor for Scots pine (0.64%) was higher than the factor 0.50% obtained with the same device and species (Montero et al. 2015). The longitudinal vibration approach resulted in the same correction factor if the two devices PLG and MTG were used, which were in the range of 0.62 to 0.76%, depending on the species. These data are similar to the 0.62% Vel_{decr}/MC_{incr} obtained by ViSCAN for Norway spruce (Unterwieser and Schickhofer 2011) and the 0.65% Vel_{decr}/MC_{incr} factor obtained by the PLG for Scots pine (Montero et al. 2015).

The differences to literature data are partly due to species, the harvesting place, and the methods of MC determination. Deviation could be also due to different dimensions of the specimens (cross-section) as studied by Wang (2008) on 30 Douglas fir specimens of the same thickness (51 mm) but different widths (51, 102, 152, 203, 254 and 305 mm) in the MC range of 5 - 79%. Table 3 shows the mean values of all devices according to species. The data obtained by different devices for the same species are very similar, in agreement with Unterwieser and Schickhofer (2011), who applied Sylvatest (0.60%) and ViSCAN (0.62%) to Norway spruce. In the present paper, the highest value was found in Salzmanian-maritime pine (0.72 - 0.76%) group and the lowest value for radiata-Scots pine group (0.62%).

Conclusions

The velocities obtained by five different devices for four species (radiata pine, Scots pine, Salzmanian pine, maritime pine) show linear relationships with MC, and the slopes are steeper below FSP than above. The measured velocities decreased with MC increment up the FSP (in the 10% to 30% range), from 30 to 36 $m s^{-1}$ per % MC change. Correction factors below FSP were proposed for the 12% reference MC. Although the correction factors are independent of the devices used (ultrasound waves, impact stress wave and longitudinal vibration), they are species-dependent while the data of the Salzmanian pine and maritime pine are similar (0.72 - 0.76%) and of the trees radiata pine and Scots pine are nearly identical with 0.62%. A wide range of MC correction factors are found in the literature due to different species, and their densities, and specimen sizes. Further, errors in the MC determination may also cause deviations.

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Table 1. Averaged data of MCs and velocities obtained from different devices.

Species	Stages	Days	MC		TOF measurements						Longitudinal vibration			
					<i>Vel</i> SylDuo		<i>Vel</i> USLab		<i>Vel</i> MST		<i>Vel</i> PLG		<i>Vel</i> MTG	
			(%)	COV (%)	(m s ⁻¹)	COV (%)	(m s ⁻¹)	COV (%)						
Radiata pine	1	0	52.7	51.8	4588	7.8	4856	9.0	4639	6.9	3978	9.8	4011	9.7
	2	12	29.2	11.5	4882	6.2	5326	6.3	5059	5.6	4336	8.0	4367	8.1
	3	24	21.3	15.3	5090	5.7	5571	5.9	5151	5.6	4490	7.9	4522	7.9
	4	38	17.7	8.9	5192	5.8	5648	5.9	5271	5.4	4590	7.9	4625	7.9
	5	52	14.8	7.4	5276	5.8	5789	5.6	5407	6.0	4676	7.9	4702	8.0
	6	66	13.6	5.8	5333	5.9	5813	5.7	5461	5.8	4733	7.9	4755	7.9
	7	87	11.6	5.2	5377	5.8	5880	5.9	5470	5.6	4775	8.0	4808	7.9
	8	109	10.1	5.5	5418	5.8	5868	7.0	5545	5.7	4815	8.0	4850	7.9
	9	136	9.1	4.6	5470	5.9	5972	5.7	5664	5.9	4855	8.0	4894	7.9
	10	150	8.9	4.1	5478	5.9	5990	5.8	5677	5.8	4870	8.0	4910	7.9
Scots pine	1	0	32.6	36.8	4689	6.0	5137	5.9	4875	5.8	4158	6.2	4198	6.1
	2	10	23.5	19.3	4912	5.4	5418	5.6	5031	5.1	4376	6.1	4411	6.0
	3	31	18.3	7.6	5072	5.7	5570	5.6	5251	5.6	4517	6.4	4547	6.2
	4	46	15.2	5.3	5212	5.5	5684	5.6	5342	5.4	4621	6.5	4658	6.3
	5	65	13.4	4.9	5272	5.7	5771	5.6	5447	5.5	4682	6.5	4716	6.6
	6	79	12.2	5.8	5319	5.6	5829	5.5	5481	5.3	4734	6.5	4770	6.5
	7	116	10.6	4.9	5358	5.6	5862	5.5	5538	5.4	4788	6.5	4824	6.5
Salzmanian pine	1	0	62.6	40.3	3761	11.1	4043	11.9	3888	10.6	3187	12.4	3211	12.3
	2	7	57.1	40.3	3786	11.2	4116	12.1	3940	10.6	3242	12.6	3284	12.3
	3	14	45.2	40.8	3938	10.3	4277	11.0	4120	10.3	3412	12.1	3439	12.0
	4	23	36.6	40.4	4025	10.3	4387	10.8	4242	9.8	3506	11.7	3534	11.6
	5	35	26.8	32.5	4197	9.8	4574	10.2	4374	9.7	3665	10.9	3711	10.8
	6	49	21.3	26.0	4315	9.3	4740	9.7	4520	8.9	3772	10.3	3808	10.3
	7	70	16.4	18.4	4490	8.5	4878	8.9	4653	8.2	3909	9.7	3952	9.5
	8	93	13.9	12.2	4568	8.1	4963	8.6	4719	8.1	3975	6.5	4023	9.5
	9	108	12.6	9.0	4641	8.1	5051	8.5	4794	9.3	4027	9.4	4072	9.5
	10	129	10.7	8.2	4673	8.0	5113	8.5	4865	7.4	4061	9.3	4099	9.4
	11	142	10.5	6.9	4706	8.0	5134	8.4	4903	7.6	4091	9.3	4130	9.3
	12	171	9.7	6.9	4734	8.0	5169	8.4	4933	7.6	4121	9.2	4168	9.0
Maritime pine	1	0	40.3	31.0	3733	8.4	4045	8.8	3856	7.8	3309	9.0	3377	8.9
	2	22	24.8	17.9	4034	9.4	4361	8.5	4148	8.9	3559	9.8	3593	10.0
	3	35	21.2	14.6	4112	8.9	4477	9.1	4254	8.4	3625	9.7	3666	9.8
	4	47	18.4	11.3	4217	8.8	4589	9.0	4319	8.5	3695	9.5	3738	9.7
	5	61	16.4	8.2	4265	8.6	4623	8.8	4371	8.6	3748	9.4	3796	9.7
	6	75	14.3	5.6	4339	8.5	4733	8.6	4439	8.2	3817	9.3	3859	9.5
	7	89	12.9	5.3	4382	8.4	4740	8.6	4489	8.1	3872	9.1	3920	9.4
	8	110	11.5	4.5	4422	8.3	4825	8.4	4553	8.3	3914	9.0	3952	9.5
	9	132	10.7	5.1	4462	8.3	4861	8.3	4614	8.3	3947	9.0	3998	9.4
	10	159	9.3	4.9	4501	8.2	4903	8.2	4695	8.2	4006	9.0	4044	9.3
	11	180	9.2	4.4	4520	8.2	4942	8.1	-*	-	4009	8.9	4049	9.0

* It was not possible to obtain measure number 11 due to problems with MST device

Table 2. Coefficients for Eq. 1 ($Vel = a \cdot MC + b \cdot Z_{rad} + c \cdot Z_{sco} + d \cdot Z_{lar} + E$) with velocity as variable including the R^2 and P-values of the predictions (below FSP).

Device	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>E</i>	R^2 (%)	<i>P</i> - value
SylDuo	-33.0	953.9	868.4	217.2	4810.5	63	0.00
USLab	-36.3	1054.0	987.0	250.2	5239.1	63	0.00
MST	-34.8	955.5	906.7	273.1	4965.7	64	0.00
PLG	-29.6	861.5	802.1	133.7	4252.4	58	0.00
MTG	-29.9	851.2	795.3	132.5	4299.1	57	0.00

Table 3.- Correction factors (k_{MC}) in % obtained for four wood species with the instruments indicated (below FSP).

Species	k_{MC} (%)					
	TOF measurements			Longit. vibration		Mean
	SylDuo	USLab	MST	PLG	MTG	
Radiata pine	0.61	0.62	0.63	0.62	0.62	0.62
Scots pine	0.62	0.58	0.64	0.63	0.63	0.62
Salzmanian pine	0.71	0.72	0.72	0.73	0.73	0.72
Maritime pine	0.75	0.76	0.77	0.76	0.76	0.76

Figure 1.- Specimens in sawmill with ends sealed

Figure 2.- Measurement setup (left – Time-of-flight device / right – PLG longitudinal vibration device)

Figure 3.- Linear regressions: mean velocities vs. MC. a) radiata pine, b) Scots pine, c) Salzmanian pine and d) maritime pine